

in the soil of the incorporated azolla and azolla incorporated with nitrogen treatment was almost the same before the residuals study, the azolla-incorporated treatment yielded higher. ■

Azolla manuring and grain yield of rice

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Azolla at 10, 20, and 30 t/ha tested at this station gave significant increase in grain yield. To determine the response of the highest level of azolla that would give a significant yield increase, a replicated trial was conducted during 1979 thaladi season. Azolla at 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, and 100 t/ha was applied in the plots, and incorporated.

Data on grain yield of rice. Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Azolla manure (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	3.9
10	4.4
20	5.0
30	5.6
40	6.2
50	6.7
60	7.3
70	7.6
80	7.8
90	8.0
100	8.0
C.D. = ($P = 0.05\%$)	465

A week later, the short-duration variety ADT31 was planted. Data on grain yield are in the table.

Yield increases in the short-duration ADT31 were significant up to 60 t azolla/ha. ■

Clay mineralogies and available phosphorus and exchangeable potassium status of some Philippine rice soils

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Clay fractions of 160 surface soil samples from 12 major rice-growing provinces in

Table 1. Clay mineralogy in relation to exchangeable potassium in Philippine soils. IRRI, 1980.^a

Exchangeable K (meq/100 g)	Dominant minerals	Major minerals	Minor minerals
< 0.1	Vermiculite, beidellite	—	Occasional halloysite
0.1–0.2	Vermiculite, beidellite	—	Montmorillonite
0.2–0.5	Montmorillonite, halloysite, x-ray amorphous material	Montmorillonite, halloysite, x-ray amorphous material	—
> 0.5	Montmorillonite	Hydrous mica	Feldspars

^aDominant = > 50%, major = 20–50%, minor = < 20%, — = not observed.

Table 2. Clay mineralogy in relation to available phosphorus in Philippine rice soils. IRRI, 1980.

Olsen P (ppm)	Dominant/major minerals ^a	Minor minerals
< 5	Halloysite/kaolinite/x-ray amorphous material	Vermiculite/beidellite/montmorillonite
5–10	Vermiculite/beidellite/montmorillonite	Halloysite/kaolinite/x-ray amorphous material
> 10	Vermiculite/beidellite/montmorillonite	Hydrous mica/feldspars

^aDominant = >50%, major = 20–50%, minor = <20%.

the Philippines were analyzed by x-ray diffractometry. The dominant compositions were vermiculite, beidellite, montmorillonite; all three minerals with and without halloysite; halloysite; and x-ray amorphous materials.

In all soils with dominant vermiculite or beidellite, the exchangeable potassium content was less than 0.1 meq/100 g; when those 2 minerals were accompanied by montmorillonite as a minor component, the exchangeable potassium value rose to 0.2 meq/100 g. In almost all other soils the exchangeable potassium content exceeded 0.2 meq/100 g, reflecting an adequate level of available potassium (Table 1).

All soils containing halloysite or x-ray amorphous material had (Olsen) available phosphorus values below 10 ppm, indicating an inadequate available phosphorus status. The mean for samples with dominant halloysite was 2 ppm; the mean for samples with x-ray amorphous material or with halloysite as a secondary component was about 5 ppm. Olsen phosphorus values for almost all other soils containing dominant beidellite, vermiculite, or montmorillonite ranged from 10 to 50 ppm (Table 2), showing a high available phosphorus status.

Farmers' experience and trials by the

Philippine Bureau of Soils showed severe potassium deficiency and lack of response to potassium fertilizers on many soils in Zambales, Pampanga, Tarlac, and Nueva Ecija Provinces, in which vermiculite and beidellite were dominant. Phosphorus deficiency appeared related to the presence of halloysite or x-ray amorphous material in the clay fraction. Soils in which montmorillonite is dominant apparently have adequate supplies of both available phosphorus and potassium.

Because soils with dominant vermiculite and beidellite clay mineralogies fix potassium and ammonium fertilizers and those with dominant halloysite and x-ray amorphous material may inactivate phosphate fertilizers, fertilizer management practices suited to such soils should be developed. ■

Development of semidwarf dryland rice cultivars tolerant of iron chlorosis

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In Maharashtra State, the high yielding semidwarf varieties such as IR8, TN1, Jaya, and their progeny are traditionally

grown in the high rainfall zone with lateritic soils (Oxisols) as a wetland, transplanted crop.

Recently rice cultivation in the arid to semiarid regions of the state was boosted with the construction of dams and a network of irrigation systems. Soils of the region are typical Vertisols, medium to deep black, having about 40–65% montmorillonitic clay, and are calcareous (pH of 8.0–9.2). Fertile soils and abundance of sunshine and irrigation water have created a good potential for rice cultivation in this nontraditional area, which is about 300,000 ha. Extension of rice cultivation to these lands during the past 4–5 years has not been successful because of the lodging habit and low fertilizer response of the tall local cultivars, and iron chlorosis encountered by the high yielding semidwarf varieties and their derivatives. In these calcareous and aerobic soils available iron is low. Submerging the soils can increase iron availability. But puddling the soil and transplanting spoil the soil structure so that the soil becomes useless for crops in

Salient features of the semidwarf mutants and local tall cultivars. Maharashtra, India.

Strain	Plant ht (cm)	Lodging score (0–4)	Days to maturity (seed to seed)	Effective tillers (no./m ²)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Local</i>					
Tuljapur 1	98	4	101	269	2.5
Jalgaon 5	115	4	104	258	2.8
Ambemohor	117	4	104	265	3.8
<i>Semidwarf mutants</i>					
A-1	78	0	105	290	3.5
A-7	81	0	108	254	3.3
A-20	90	1	106	225	3.3

the following season. Thus, a rice crop on these soils must be a drilled dryland crop.

All the semidwarf varieties and derivatives tried so far have the Dee-Geo-Woo-Gen dwarfing gene, which probably has tight linkage with the gene or genes that confer susceptibility to iron deficiency. The local tall cultivars are efficient in extracting iron from these soils, and hence do not normally show symptoms of iron chlorosis. To develop alternative sources of the dwarfing habit, the local tall cultivars were subjected to mutagenesis. Semidwarf mutants isolated

in the M₂ generation were evaluated in the M₅ along with the checks in 22.5-cm spaced rows fertilized with 80 kg N and 40 kg P₂O₅/ha. The salient features of some of the semidwarf mutants and the tall checks are presented in the table. The mutants are tolerant of iron chlorosis, are nonlodging, and have good yield potential. Preliminary indications are that they are fertilizer responsive. Experiments on the agronomic manipulation of the mutants and their evaluation on a wider scale are under progress. ■

Effect of flooding depth on nitrogen, phosphate, and potash availability and change in electrochemical behavior of puddled and unpuddled soils

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A field experiment on water management of rice was conducted at Pantnagar, India. Total nitrogen content and availability of phosphorus and potassium increased with water depth (Table 1, 2).

pH decreased slightly with increasing depth of submergence in puddled soil, but not in unpuddled soil. The specific conductance value, however, increased with depth of flooding in both puddled and unpuddled soils. No change in the specific conductance value was observed in the saturation and rainfed treatments (Table 1, 2). ■

Table 1. Effect of depth of submergence on availability of nitrogen, phosphate, and potash; and on pH and specific conductance in puddled soils. 1973 wet season, Pantnagar, India.

Depth of submergence	Total nitrogen (%)	Available nutrients (kg/ha)		soil pH	Specific conductance (mmho/cm) at 25°C
		P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O		
15 cm – 1 cm	0.156	105.5	168.2	7.5	0.65
5 cm – field capacity	0.151	99.0	165.3	7.5	0.50
1 cm – field capacity	0.149	81.7	161.8	7.7	0.45
36 cm total water use (50% of total water use)	0.147	81.7	161.9	7.7	0.45
Rainfed	0.148	81.8	161.8	7.7	0.45

Table 2. Effect of depth of submergence on availability of nitrogen, phosphate, and potash; and on soil pH and specific conductance in unpuddled soils. 1973 wet season, Pantnagar, India.^a

Depth of submergence until 21 DSE	Depth of submergence from 21 DSE to maturity	Total N (%)	Available nutrients (kg/ha)		Soil pH	Specific conductance (mmho/cm) at 25°C
			P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O		
1 cm – FC	15 cm – 1 cm	0.18	85.9	156.5	7.6	0.60
1 cm – FC	5 cm – FC	0.15	82.4	141.1	7.6	0.60
1 cm – FC	1 cm – FC	0.11	76.3	127.7	7.7	0.45
5 cm – 1 cm	15 cm – 1 cm	0.18	94.6	164.4	7.6	0.63
5 cm – 1 cm	5 cm – FC	0.16	78.8	151.2	7.6	0.50
5 cm – FC	15 cm – 1 cm	0.13	76.6	120.9	7.7	0.45
5 cm – FC	5 cm – FC	0.18	81.7	168.0	7.5	0.62
5 cm – FC	5 cm – FC	0.14	77.6	164.6	7.6	0.52
5 cm – FC	1 cm – FC	0.13	75.8	141.1	7.7	0.45

^aDSE = days after seedling establishment, FC = field capacity.